

Safe management of Cyprinid herpesvirus 3-induced mortalities of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) by silaging process

Remigiusz Panicz^a, Piotr Eljasik^{a,*}, Agnieszka Troszok^b, Małgorzata Sobczak^a, Sławomir Lisiecki^a, Arkadiusz Nędzarek^c, Jacek Sadowski^c

^a Department of Meat Sciences, Faculty of Food Sciences and Fisheries, West Pomeranian University of Technology in Szczecin, 4 Kazimierza Królewicza Street, 71–550 Szczecin, Poland

^b Institute of Ichthyobiology and Aquaculture, Polish Academy of Sciences, Chybie, Poland

^c Department of Aquatic Bioengineering and Aquaculture, Faculty of Food Sciences and Fisheries, West Pomeranian University of Technology in Szczecin, 4 Kazimierza Królewicza Street, 71–550 Szczecin, Poland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

By-streams
Cell culture
KHV
Inactivation
Organic fertilizer

ABSTRACT

In open farming systems, fish losses are unfortunate daily finding, hence a simple, safe and highly adaptable method is needed to manage dead fish. The aim of this study was to develop three silaging methods of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) carcasses to identify cost-effective, eco-friendly, and efficient method to turn dead fish into organic fertiliser and to determine whether Cyprinid herpesvirus 3 (CyHV-3) can be inactivated during a 34-weeks trial. In our study, dead fish were chopped, minced with starter bacteria culture and wheat bran (Basic), water and wheat bran starter (Hydrated) or Bokashi commercial mix (Commercial), and placed in a 1 L jars (in quadruplicates). The CyHV-3 infectivity potential was assessed by two cell cultures and expression of the virus genes classified into three temporal kinetic classes. The feasibility of the silaging method and selection of the best method assessed by pH monitoring, characterisation of the odour profile, elemental analysis and calculating the cost of the in-farm silaging. Cell cultures and the subsequent gene expression analyses showed that the virus was successfully inactivated in the Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silages, confirming their safety. Among the three silaging methods, the Hydrated was the cost-effective one; however, concerning the other features (odour profile, feasibility and final pH level), the Basic was selected as the most promising for implementation. Additionally, elemental analysis showed that the level of nutrients in Basic silage was higher than in commonly used natural fertilisers, while the content of heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Zn) met the official recommendations for organic fertilisers. The study provides premise of an effective method of silaging of dead carp that offers pathogen inactivation (via combination of decreased pH and microbial activity), turns common by-stream into a valuable product and increases profitability of the farm in a sustainable and cost-effective way.

1. Introduction

Aquaculture production has experienced an annual average growth rate of 5.3% between 2001 and 2018, constituting in 2016–2018 approx. 46% of global seafood supply (FAO, 2020). It is estimated that this sector will have to supply ~100 million tonnes per year by 2025 (Sosa-Villalobos et al., 2016). Several lines of effort are in progress, both nationally and internationally, to increase aquaculture production and, at the same time, to minimise adverse factors such as diseases. Mortalities mostly caused by bacteria, viruses, fungi and protozoan parasites remain the

primary concern in aquaculture, as infectious diseases cause the greatest economic losses, globally estimated at US\$ 1.05 to US\$ 9.58 billion/year (Shinn et al., 2015). Direct susceptibility of the host to the various aforementioned disease agents is mainly related to both the farming conditions such as water temperature (Gilad et al., 2003) that stress physiological and immune systems of fish, and the susceptibility of animals to such exposure (Bush et al., 2010; Salama and Murray, 2011). Additionally, certain rearing methods, such as cages and earthen ponds in marine or freshwater systems, can facilitate pathogen exchange between farmed and wild populations of aquatic organisms (Johansen

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: rpanicz@zut.edu.pl (R. Panicz), peljasik@zut.edu.pl (P. Eljasik), agnieszka.troszok@golysz.pan.pl (A. Troszok), malgorzata.sobczak@zut.edu.pl (M. Sobczak), slawomir.lisiecki@zut.edu.pl (S. Lisiecki), arkadiusz.nedzarek@zut.edu.pl (A. Nędzarek), jsadowski@zut.edu.pl (J. Sadowski).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2022.101116>

Received 14 December 2021; Received in revised form 4 April 2022; Accepted 4 April 2022

2352-5134/© 2022 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

et al., 2011; Panicz et al., 2020). This situation may lead to both pathogen spillover (Krkošek et al., 2006) or spillback (Kelly et al., 2009), thus reducing the profitability and sustainability of fish farming of, e.g., salmonids and cyprinids (Jansen et al., 2012; Leung and Bates, 2013; Salama and Murray, 2011).

Herpesviruses of fish and amphibians are grouped together and form the family of Alloherpesviridae. Besides this family, the order of Herpesvirales includes viruses that specifically infect reptiles, birds, mammals (Herpesviridae) and molluscs (Malacoherpesviridae). Currently, the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV), based on the results of large-scale comparisons between the deduced amino acid sequences of DNA genes, identified 12 species of alloherpesviruses, 10 of which infect fish. At least 11 alloherpesviruses cause significant economic losses to aquaculture, with *Cyprinid herpesvirus 3* (CyHV-3) as the primary agent which, since the first description in the late 1990s, has been causing important economic losses worldwide in all strains of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) (Kibenge and Godoy, 2016). Recently numerous outbreaks of koi herpesvirus disease (KHVD) were reported in Asia, Europe and America (Rahmati-Holasoo et al., 2016; Ahmadvand et al., 2020; Ababneh et al., 2020; Bergmann et al., 2020). Based on the severe clinical manifestations of disease, mortality rates range from 80% to 100% (Dixon et al., 2009; Hedrick et al., 2000). The success of CyHV-3 is inherently related to its apparent ability to (i) intricately interact with the host defences (Hanson et al., 2011), (ii) establish long-term latency within the host cells (Eide et al., 2011) and (iii) remain infectious in the natural environment, such as turbid, eutrophic water (Minamoto et al., 2009), aquatic vertebrate and invertebrate species (Fabian et al., 2013), faeces from infected fish (Dishon et al., 2005) and dead fish (Fournier et al., 2012). The information on the persistence of CyHV-3 DNA in the fish farm environment (water, sediments, reed zones) is crucial for preventing outbreaks of the KHVD (Minamoto et al., 2009; Shimizu et al., 2006). However, information on the infectivity and virulence of CyHV-3 present in mortal (morts) fish is scarce.

Pond aquaculture is an important component of freshwater aquaculture in Europe and globally. The main target species cultured in the European pond culture is common carp contributing to 3.8% (0.17 t) of the total inland aquaculture production (4.4 mln t) during 2015–2016 (FAO FishStat, 2022). Common carp is produced in two- or three-year production cycles, and differences in pond farming efficacy between Poland, Czech Republic, Hungary, Germany, Russia and Ukraine and are mostly related to the climate conditions, pond productivity and feeding strategy. The unique feature of extensive carp farming in Europe is a single harvest period (October–November) and a very short market season concentrated around Christmas (and Easter in Germany), strongly linked with the tradition of carp consumption around these times (Lasner et al., 2020). This biased farming mode, in which farmers hope to cover all incurred expenses from the income restricted to the festive seasons, keeps farmers on the brink of profitability. Farms have limited options of specialisation, vertical integration, diversification or upscaling, and domestic markets are being eroded by the changing consumer preferences, price competition and imbalances at the value chain (Lasner et al., 2020; Raftowicz et al., 2020). Even if some farms may benefit from the additional income from tourism or subsidies for environmental and cultural services, one of the main threats for their sustainability are disease outbreaks (e.g., caused by CyHV-3) which are difficult to predict and avoid in an open farming system. Several studies facing this problem were developed, e.g. immunisation with KV3 vaccine (Perelberg et al., 2008) or recombinant ORF56–57 deleted virus (Boutier et al., 2017), introgression of resistance genes into cultured susceptible strains (Tadmor-Levi et al., 2017) and application of antiviral medications (Troszok et al., 2018). For example, KV3 vaccine (Phibro Animal Health Corporation) currently available only in Indonesia and Israel, because of residual virulence of the vaccine virus and the danger of transmission to naïve individuals and undetermined risk of reversion to strongly pathogenic phenotype (Boutier et al., 2015).

Aforementioned solutions require further studies, and it is unknown when the safe methods preventing high mortalities caused by CyHV-3 will be available.

Depending on the stage of the farming cycle and the causative agent of the losses (natural mortality, predation or diseases), farmers have to include fish wastes in their budgets and additionally cover all costs related to the management of moribund or dead fish from the ponds. Available technologies (e.g. drying) to manage dead fish need further development to decrease high costs related to energy consumption and fulfil sustainable development goals. Among the low-cost methods, silaging has been successfully applied in food sector to process fish and their by-products (Gao et al., 1992; Desai et al., 2022), however information on the use of this method to manage dead fish from disease outbreaks are scarce and needs to be elaborated. Moreover, at the same time freshwater aquaculture sector urgently seek cost-effective and sustainable methods to safely manage problematic side streams such as fish mortalities. Therefore, the aim of the study was to propose a cost-effective silaging method of common carp mortalities caused by CyHV-3 to produce soil fertiliser and to assess whether the silaging process effectively reduces the infectivity of CyHV-3.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. KHVD outbreak and identification of CyHV-3

Infected fish ($n = 30$) with clear KHVD symptoms (Supplementary Fig. S1) (Walster, 1999) were collected from the Fisheries Experimental Station (FES), located in Nowe Czarowo, Poland (N: 53° 120 36' E: 14° 270 48'). In FES, cases of KHVD outbreak were previously noted (Bergmann et al., 2006; Panicz et al., 2020), and mortalities of cage-cultured common carp were recorded on 14 January 2019 and lasted for approx. three weeks. During the outbreak, recorded water temperature was permissive for CyHV-3 development (above 15 °C), and mortality rate reached 65%.

To confirm the plausible causative agent of mortality, newly dead fish ($n = 10$) were delivered to the laboratory. Samples of gill and organ pools (kidney, liver, gut and spleen) were used for DNA extraction using High Pure PCR Template Preparation Kit (Roche, Switzerland) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The quality and quantity of DNA isolates were assessed by separation in 1.5% agarose gel and spectrophotometric measurements using a NanoDrop 2000 (Thermo Scientific, USA). The extracted DNA was tested using qPCR according to Gilad et al. (2004). Real-time PCR was conducted on LightCycler® 480 II (Roche, Switzerland) using LightCycler® 480 Probes Master (Roche, Switzerland), 0.4 μM of each primer, 0.1 μM of hydrolysis probe and 2 μL of DNA template in a final volume of 20 μL in the following conditions: 1 step of activation at 95 °C for 2 min followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 3 s and amplification/extension at 60 °C for 30 s. The qPCR curves were compared against negative and positive controls. Detection of the CyHV-3 DNA in the three types of silage at the end of the trial was performed using end-point PCR using primers KHV-TKf/KHV-TKr and KHV-TKfn/KHV-TKrn (Bercovier et al., 2005; Way, 2007, unpublished) and qPCR following protocols provided above (Supplementary Table S1).

2.2. Preparation of fish silage, changes in pH and odour profiles

Dead common carps collected during the KHVD outbreak were used to prepare three silages in quadruplicates ($n = 4$ per silage type) as follows. Fish carcasses were chopped and minced using Bauknecht (Predom Mesko, Poland) with a 5 mm mesh diameter sieve. The minced fish (250 g) was placed in 1 L glass jars, and other ingredients were added depending on the type (Fig. 1). In the Basic type of silage, 60 g of wheat bran (BIO-RAK s.c., Poland) and 0.5 g of the BIOBAK SAL (FRUTAROM Savory Solutions Austria GmbH, Austria), containing *Pediococcus pentosaceus* ($> 6 \times 10^9$ cfu g⁻¹), *Staphylococcus carnosus* ($>$

Fig. 1. Overview of the silaging experimental design, with raw materials composition of the Basic, Hydrated and Commercial and cost calculation per tonne of fish. Axis indicates pH and odour profile sampling points across 34 weeks trial. The costs provided in EUR were calculated based on conversion rate of the National Bank of Poland (1 EUR = 4.5 PLN) from 23rd December of 2020.

6×10^9 cfu g^{-1}), *Staphylococcus xyloso* ($> 1.2 \times 10^{10}$ cfu g^{-1}) in a glucose-containing medium, were added. In the Hydrated type of silage, 540 g of sourdough resulting from the fermentation of wheat bran:water mixture at 1:8, as well as 0.5 g of BIOBAK SAL, were added. The Commercial type of silage contained 60 g of the commercial EM Bokashi starter (Greenland Technologia EM sp. z o.o., Poland), containing cereal bran, water, Efektywne Mikroorganizmy® and molasses (certificate no. PZH/HT-2711/2012). Each type of silage was thoroughly mixed, and pH was measured using a portable pH meter (CP-411, Elmetron, Poland). Jars were sealed and stored at room temperature for 34 weeks. Subsequently, pH and odour profiles were assessed in the 1st, 3rd, 6th, 9th and 34th week of the trial. The pH was measured in quadruplicates for each type of silage at every time point of the trial using the portable pH meter (CP-411, Elmetron, Poland) with a glass penetrating electrode. Before the analysis, the pH meter was calibrated using standard phosphate buffers (pH 4 and 7). Between measurements, the electrode was rinsed thoroughly with distilled water. Odour profile was evaluated for each type of silage at each time point of the trial by a trained team of four (PN-ISO, 6658; 1998). Odour descriptors of the samples were immediately assessed after opening the jars containing each silage type.

2.3. Elemental analysis

At the end of the trial, the Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silage samples ($n = 4$ per silage type) were dissolved as described by Mistri et al. (2020). Samples of 1.0 ± 0.1 g (wet weight) were digested in 10 mL of concentrated ultrapure HNO_3 (Merck, Germany) in a Speed-wave Xpert high-pressure microwave mineralizer (Berghof, Germany). The DAK-100 reaction vessels used were made of TFM™-PTFE (second-generation polytetrafluoroethylene), and the digestion conditions were as follows: power – 2000 W, hold time – 25 min, and temperature – 200 °C. After cooling, samples were transferred into volumetric flasks (25 mL) and diluted to the mark with deionized water (18.2 MΩ). Element measurements in the silage samples were carried out with a Hitachi ZA3000 Series Polarized Zeeman Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (Hitachi High-Technologies Corporation, Japan) equipped with a Zeeman background correction system. Ca, K, Na, Mg were

measured using flame atomic absorption spectroscopy (FAAS) in an air–acetylene flame. Al, Cd, Cu, Fe, Pb and Zn were measured using graphite furnace atomic absorption spectroscopy (GFAAS). Radiation sources for elements were hollow-cathode lamps (HCL, Hitachi High-Technologies Corporation, Japan) at the appropriate wavelengths (in nm): 309.3 (for Al); 422.7 (for Ca); 228.8 (for Cd); 324.8 (for Cu); 248.3 (for Fe); 766.5 (for K); 285.2 (for Mg); 589.0 (for Na); 283.3 (for Pb); 213.9 (for Zn). The following matrix modifiers were also used: palladium (0.2% Pd in 5% HNO_3 , SIGMATIK, Poland); $Mg(NO_3)_2$ and $NH_4H_2PO_4$ (both 1000 mg L^{-1} , Merck, Germany), along with the caesium chloride–lanthanum chloride buffer solution acc. To Schinkel for atomic absorption spectroscopy (10 g L^{-1} CsCl and 100 g L^{-1} La, MERCK, Germany). Calibration curves were established using certified standard solutions (1000 mg L^{-1}) from Scharlau (Spain) for Mg, Ca, K, Na and Fe, and from Merck (Germany) for Al, Cd, Cu, Pb and Zn. Limits of Quantification (LOQ) were as follows: 0.3 mg kg^{-1} (for Ca, K); 0.03 mg kg^{-1} (for Mg); 0.15 mg kg^{-1} (for Na); 1.0 μg kg^{-1} (for Al, Cd, Pb); 1.5 μg kg^{-1} (for Cu, Fe); 0.2 μg kg^{-1} (for Zn). The obtained results were assessed for accuracy and precision using certified reference material of Fish Muscle ERM BB422 (European Reference Materials, European Commission – Joint Research Centre, Institute for Reference Materials and Measurements, Belgium). The recovery of elements was within 95–105%, and precision for reference material was 1.3–11.4% (Supplementary Table S2).

Phosphorus (P) was quantified colorimetrically in the same sample solutions as the other elements. The employed method, described by Jastrzębska (2009), used ammonium molybdate and ascorbic acid as reducers, forming molybdenum blue. Absorbance at $\lambda = 882$ nm was measured on a UV–VIS spectrophotometer Spectroquant Pharo 300 (Merck, Germany). The level of P_2O_5 in the silage samples were calculated according to the Journal of Laws 183, item 1229 of the Ministry of Economy (2010). Organic sulphur (S-SO₄) was determined using the modified Barsley–Lancaster method (Ostrowska et al., 1991). The content of nitrogen and organic matter in the silage samples were determined according to the AOAC (Association of Official Analytical Chemists) procedures (Latimer, 2019). The content of nitrogen was assessed by digesting 0.500 ± 0.01 g of silage samples in the mixture of

95% sulfuric acid (Chempur, Poland) and 30% hydrogen peroxide (Chempur, Poland) in equal volumes of 10 mL each, together with a catalyst – Kjeldahl tablets (MERCK KgaA, Germany). Digestion was performed using Heating Digester DK6 and DK8 (VELP Scientifica, Italy), following the thermal profile of 30 min at 180 °C, 30 min at 280 °C and 30 min at 380 °C. To assess the level of organic matter in the silage samples, dry matter was first assessed by drying samples in an oven at 105 °C for 24 h, and subsequent incineration at 550 °C for 6 h.

2.4. Cell cultures

Common carp brain (CCB, ECACC 10072802) cell line was obtained from the European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures. Koi carp fin (KF1, ECACC 10072801) cell line was kindly provided by Prof. Dieter Steinhagen and Dr Mikołaj Adamek from the Fish Disease Research Unit, University of Veterinary Medicine, Hannover. The cell lines were maintained as previously described (Troszok et al., 2018). For all experiments, cells were inoculated at a density $1.5 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

2.5. Virus

The CyHV-3 was used as a positive control for cell culture experiments. The strain was isolated at the Department of Fish Diseases, National Veterinary Research Institute, Pulawy, Poland, in 2005 from infected common carp (Adamek et al., 2014; Rakus et al., 2012). Subsequently, the virus was propagated in a CCB cell culture and stored in aliquots at – 80 °C until used. Viral titre estimated using CCB cells and the Spearman and Karber method (Ramakrishnan, 2016) was $1.5 \times 10^4 \text{ TCID}_{50} \text{ mL}^{-1}$ (tissue culture infective dose). To obtain the proper control of the silage extracts, the virus was passed through a 0.45 µm syringe filter similarly to silage extracts and further called “filtered virus”. Passing the virus through the 0.45 µm syringe filter decreased its titre to $1.6 \times 10^2 \text{ TCID}_{50} \text{ mL}^{-1}$.

2.6. Preparation of silage extracts

The Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silage samples were individually homogenised with Dulbecco’s Modified Eagle’s Medium (DMEM), (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) in a glass homogeniser at a proportion 1 g of each silage type per 9 mL of DMEM. The homogenate was centrifuged at 1462 rcf, for 15 min, at room temperature. The clear part of the extract was mixed with DMEM at the proportion 2:3, respectively, to obtain 4% silage extract. pH was adjusted with HCl or NaOH to the value in between 7.2 and 7.4. The silage extracts were passed through a 0.45 µm syringe filter. The silage extracts were freshly prepared before each repeat of the experiment.

2.7. Determination of the highest possible dose of silage extracts

To determine the highest possible dose of silage extracts CCB and KF1 cells were inoculated on 96-well plates. After 20 h, the medium was removed. Silage extracts (4%) were serially diluted with DMEM at the proportion 1:2 to obtain 2%, 1%, 0.5% and 0.25% of silage extracts. Dilutions, as well as control DMEM, were applied onto the cells in triplicates, 50 µL per well. Incubation lasted 2 h to imitate conditions that were used for the infection of cells with CyHV-3. At the end of the incubation time, the silage extracts were removed, and phenol-red free culture medium was added to each well. After 20 h, cell survival was evaluated with a crystal violet (CV) assay as previously described (Saotome et al., 1989; Troszok et al., 2018), with modifications. Briefly, the culture medium was removed. Cells were washed two times with 100 µL of PBS and set in 100 µL PBS, and 100 µL of fixative (methanol: 80% acetic acid at the v/v ratio 3:1) was added to each well. After 10 min, the fixative was removed. The cells were washed two times with 200 µL of methanol, with 5 min incubation step at each wash. The cells were stained with 30 µL CV solution (0.5% CV in 20% methanol) for

30 min. The excess of CV was removed with tap-water. Subsequently, 1% SDS was used to dissolve the stained cells. Absorbance was read at $\lambda = 590 \text{ nm}$. The absorbance read from the silage extract-treated cells was calculated as the percentage of absorbance read from control-treated cells; therefore, cell viability was expressed as percent of control.

2.8. Examination of silage extracts in cytopathic effect assay

CCB and KF1 cells were inoculated on 24-well plates and cultured for 20 h. Subsequently, the medium was removed, and the cells were treated in quadruple with 297 µL of silage extract per well or with $100 \times$ diluted filtered virus (finally reaching $1.6 \text{ TCID}_{50} \text{ mL}^{-1}$) or with control DMEM. The maximum concentration of 4% of each silage extract (Basic, Hydrated and Commercial) was used for KF1 cell line, and 0.5% extract of the Basic silage, 1% extract of the Hydrated silage and 1% extract of the Commercial silage were used for CCB cell line. After 2 h of incubation/infection step, the solutions were replaced with 0.5 mL of culture medium. The cells were regularly observed under a microscope at a magnification of $100 \times$ for the appearance of cytopathic effect for up to 27–42 days, until the uninfected control cells died. The experiment was repeated five times for each cell line.

2.9. Examination of silage extracts in viral gene expression assay

CCB and KF1 cells were inoculated on 6-well plates and cultured for 20 h. Subsequently, the medium was removed, and the cells were treated with 1.5 mL of silage extract per well or with $1000 \times$ diluted unfiltered virus (finally reaching $1.5 \times 10^1 \text{ TCID}_{50} \text{ mL}^{-1}$) or with $1000 \times$ diluted filtered virus (finally reaching $1.6 \times 10^{-1} \text{ TCID}_{50} \text{ mL}^{-1}$) or with control DMEM. The maximum concentration of 4% of each silage extract (Basic, Hydrated and Commercial) was used for KF1 cell line, and 0.5% extract of the Basic silage, 1% extract of the Hydrated silage and 1% extract of the Commercial silage were used for CCB cell line. After 2 h of incubation/infection step, the solutions were replaced with 2 mL of culture medium. The cells were incubated for 6 days. At the end of incubation, the medium was removed, and the cells were dissolved in Tri Reagent LS (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany).

2.10. RNA extraction, cDNA synthesis and RT-qPCR for viral gene expression

Total RNA was extracted from cell lines CCB and KF1 ($n = 5$ each) using Tri Reagent LS (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) according to the standard isolation protocol. The quantity and quality of RNA was assessed using NanoDrop 2000 (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA) and 2% agarose gel electrophoresis; the 260/280 ratio for all samples was approx. 2.0, and no signs of degradation were observed. Reverse transcription was performed immediately after RNA extraction, using 1 µg of RNA and Transcriptor First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Roche, Switzerland), according to the manufacturer’s instructions, with anchored oligo(dT)₁₈ primers. The activity of CyHV-3 genes (*orf78*, capsid maturation protease; *orf134*, viral homologue of interleukin 10; *orf3*, transcription factor) and common carp glucokinase (*gluc*) as control gene were assessed according to Troszok et al. (2018). Real-time PCR reactions were performed on LightCycler® 480 II (Roche, Switzerland) using LightCycler® 480 SYBR Green I Master (Roche, Switzerland), 0.1 µM of each primer and 1 µL of cDNA templates in the final volume of 20 µL, in duplicates. Thermal profile for the reactions was as follow: initial activation at 95 °C for 10 min, followed by 45 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 10 s, annealing at 60 °C for 10 s and extending at 72 °C for 15 s. Melting curve analysis (65–95 °C) was conducted at the end of each PCR thermal profile to ensure the specificity of amplification.

2.11. Statistical analysis

For each element and pH value tested (in triplicate and quadruplicates respectively) within each silage type, mean and standard deviation were calculated using STATISTICA v.13.01 (TIBCO, USA). The normality of all data was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test, and the homogeneity of variance was tested with Levene's test. The significance of differences in the average content of metals and levels of pH between the silage types (Basic, Hydrated and Commercial) was assessed using Tukey's Honestly Significant difference test, and significance was claimed at $P = 0.05$ or lower. The significance of differences in the toxicity assays was determined with paired t test. The changes of pH were visualised using the R-package ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016). The graphical abstract and Figures were created with BioRender (www.biorender.com).

3. RESULTS

3.1. CyHV-3 as the etiologic agent of koi herpesvirus disease outbreak

The observed clinical symptoms clearly suggested that CyHV-3 was the agent causing carp mortality. Observation was also confirmed with real-time PCR analysis. In all analysed samples (gills and organ pools), CyHV-3 DNA was identified (Fig. 2a), and the Ct values for gills and pooled organs ranged from 18.23 to 31.94. After the 34-weeks trial, CyHV-3 DNA was detected in all samples (Fig. 2b), and the Ct values ranged from 30.98 to 37.86.

3.2. Changes in pH value during storage of fish silage

The pH value of three tested types of silages (Basic, Hydrated, Commercial) differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$). The difference was

clearly visible at the beginning (0–1 week) and from the 9th week of storage onwards (Fig. 3). At the beginning of the experiment, the highest pH was observed in the Basic type, which was approx. 1.02–1.19 (16.6–19.4%) higher than in the Hydrated and Commercial types. However, the observed differences in pH were insignificant ($P > 0.05$). During the 34 weeks of storage of the silages, changes in pH were observed, but the size and direction of these changes were different for the examined silage types and depended on time of storage. The greatest decrease in pH was observed after 1 week of storage. In the Basic type, pH decreased by approx. 24.6% (to 4.62), in the Hydrated type by approx. 5.3% (to 4.68), and in the Commercial type by 4.9% (to 4.86). In the following weeks (up to 9th week) of storage, changes in the pH of the silages were insignificant. Only in the case of the Hydrated type, a constant increase in pH of about 5.5–8.3% was observed from the 3rd week of storage. The increase resulted in the highest pH (6.12) at the end of the storage period (34 weeks), which was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher than in the Basic (5.11) and Commercial (5.15) types. In the two latter cases, pH increase of 6.7% and 2.3% was recorded at 34 weeks, respectively. Analysis of the entire storage period of the silages shows that the Basic pH decreased by 1.02 (16.6%), the Hydrated pH increased by 1.18 (23.9%) and the Commercial pH was at the same level as at baseline.

The changes in pH of the stored silages were reflected by shifts in the odour profiles (Table 1). At the beginning of the experiment, all types of silages were characterised by a typical odour of fish. During the first storage phase, in which the pH of all samples decreased, the silage odour changed to acidic or acidic with perceptible hydrogen sulphide. Acidic odour was noticeable during the further storage of the Basic and Commercial types, but was more intense in the former. At the same time, odour of sourdough was detected in the Basic type, and that of silage was detected in the Commercial type. At 34 weeks of storage, both silage types (Basic and Commercial) also had an alcohol-yeast odour, which could indicate the beginning of the alcoholic fermentation process. Only in the case of the Hydrated type, a very unpleasant acidic-faecal odour was detected throughout the storage period.

3.3. Levels of elements in fish silages

When comparing the chemical composition of the three types of silage, significant ($P \leq 0.05$) differences in dry matter, organic matter, P_2O_5 and macro- (N, K, Ca, Mg, S_{org}) and micronutrients (Fe, Zn, Cu, B, Mo, Cl) essential for plants were found (Table 2). The lowest quantities of dry matter, organic matter, P_2O_5 and elements were found in the Hydrated type, which resulted from its higher degree of hydration. The Basic and Commercial types did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$) in organic matter content, P_2O_5 , Ca, Mo, N and S_{org} . The highest content of K, Mg, Fe, Zn, Cu was reported for the Commercial type, that was approximately 42%, 52%, 39%, 47% and 51% higher, compared with the Basic type, and 3–5.5 times higher than Hydrated silage type.

3.4. The highest possible dose of silage extracts

In the pre-experiments, the CCB cell line appeared to be very susceptible to treatment with silage extracts. The higher concentrations of the extracts potentially disrupted the cell monolayer, preventing the distinguishment of the cytopathic effect. The changes were observed as soon as 20 h post treatment. In contrast, the KF1 cell line appeared to be resistant to the silage extracts and demonstrated good stability after the treatment. The observations concerning the CCB cell line were supported by the CV assay. The increasing concentrations of the silage extracts decreased the survival of the cells. Nevertheless, the KF1 cell line retained the cell monolayer after treatment with the highest (4%) concentration of silage extracts. For this reason, 4% concentration of all silage extracts (Basic, Hydrated and Commercial) was selected for further experiments with the KF1 cell line, although the survival of KF1 cells decreased by up to 28% after incubation with an extract of the Basic

Fig. 2. Electrophoresis of Cyprinid herpesvirus-3 (CyHV-3) detection in DNA extracts from common carp mortalities (A) and Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silages (B). Numbers and letters in part A refer to fish ID (1–6) and (G) gill or (P) organ pool samples (kidney, liver, gut and spleen) analysed for exemplary fish with clear koi herpesvirus disease symptoms. Numbers in the part B refer to the biological repetitions of analysed types of silages (1–4). K+ refer to CyHV-3 positive control, K– refer to no template control, M refer to GeneRuler 100 bp DNA, Thermo Fisher Scientific (0.1–1 kbp, thicker band indicate 500 bp). Bands in lanes between molecular marker indicate the 348-bp CyHV-3 amplicon.

Fig. 3. Changes in the pH of the Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silages made from fish with clear koi herpesvirus disease symptoms during the entire storage period. Shaded areas represent SD of measurements in sampling point. Different superscripts in each sampling point indicate significant difference between variants at $P \leq 0.05$.

Table 1
Changes of the sensory profile of the Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silages during the trail.

Time points of silaging process (week)	Type of silage		
	Basic	Hydrated	Commercial
0	rotting fish	rotting fish	rotting fish
1	silage-rotten eggs	rotten eggs	acidic (mild)
3	acidic- sourdough	acidic- faecal	acidic-silage
6	acidic- sourdough (intensive)	acidic- faecal	acidic-silage
9	acidic- sourdough (very intensive)	acidic- faecal	acidic-silage (mild)
34	acidic- sourdough -yeast-alcoholic	acidic- faecal	acidic-silage with mild yeast-alcoholic scent

silage (Table 3). Owing to the potent disruption that was observed in the CCB cell monolayer, the maximum concentrations of the silage extracts selected for further experiments did not decrease the CCB cell viability by more than 20% (Table 4). These concentrations were 0.5% for the Basic silage, 1% for the Hydrated silage and 1% for the Commercial silage.

3.5. Assessment of cytopathic effect

No cytopathic effects (CPEs) were observed in CCB and KF1 cells treated with the DMEM only or silage extracts. In almost all virus-infected CCB and KF1 cells showed CPE. Only in one out of five repeats carried out with the KF1 cell line, in one out of four virus-infected wells, the CPE did not appear.

Table 2
Concentrations of elements in the Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silages at the end of the trail.

Elements	Type of silage			Effect of silage type
	Basic	Hydrated	Commercial	
Na (mg g ⁻¹)	0.506 ^a ± 0.045	0.205 ^b ± 0.001	0.475 ^a ± 0.011	*
K (mg g ⁻¹)	3.12 ^b ± 0.26	1.56 ^c ± 0.42	4.41 ^a ± 0.26	**
Ca (mg g ⁻¹)	9.26 ^a ± 1.97	3.82 ^b ± 1.66	8.34 ^a ± 1.23	**
Mg (mg g ⁻¹)	0.64 ^b ± 0.13	0.23 ^c ± 0.02	0.97 ^a ± 0.07	**
Fe (mg g ⁻¹)	0.033 ^b ± 0.004	0.008 ^c ± 0.002	0.046 ^a ± 0.006	**
Zn (mg g ⁻¹)	0.030 ^b ± 0.002	0.013 ^c ± 0.006	0.045 ^a ± 0.005	**
Cu (mg g ⁻¹)	0.001 ^b ± 0.0003	0.0004 ^c ± 0.0001	0.002 ^a ± 0.0001	**
Mn (mg g ⁻¹)	0.026 ^a ± 0.009	0.005 ^b ± 0.003	0.017 ^a ± 0.002	**
Al (mg g ⁻¹)	0.041 ± 0.019	0.032 ± 0.007	0.052 ± 0.022	n.s.
Pb (µg g ⁻¹)	0.016 ± 0.014	0.008 ± 0.003	0.025 ± 0.019	n.s.
Cd (µg g ⁻¹)	0.014 ^b ± 0.002	0.007 ^c ± 0.001	0.024 ^a ± 0.007	**
Cr (µg g ⁻¹)	0.062 ± 0.012	0.044 ± 0.035	0.059 ± 0.011	n.s.
Co (µg g ⁻¹)	0.017 ^a ± 0.004	0.007 ^b ± 0.001	0.019 ^a ± 0.004	**
Mo (µg g ⁻¹)	0.219 ^a ± 0.069	0.052 ^b ± 0.011	0.216 ^a ± 0.056	*
Ni (µg g ⁻¹)	0.261 ^a ± 0.088	0.077 ^b ± 0.012	0.211 ^a ± 0.052	*
P ₂ O ₅ (% of ww)	1.35 ^a ± 0.21	0.72 ^b ± 0.16	1.28 ^a ± 0.08	**
S _{org} (% of ww)	0.058 ^a ± 0.010	0.025 ^b ± 0.001	0.048 ^a ± 0.017	**
N (% of ww)	2.34 ^a ± 0.11	0.99 ^b ± 0.09	2.42 ^a ± 0.11	**
Dry matter (%)	35.72 ^a ± 0.65	8.74 ^b ± 0.91	31.15 ^c ± 2.15	**
Organic matter (% of dw)	90.84 ^a ± 1.09	81.68 ^b ± 2.95	89.61 ^a ± 1.12	**

Means in each row followed by different letters are significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$). Data represent means ± SD. Significance of influence: n.s. – non-significant, ww – wet weight, dw – dry weight, * $P \leq 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$.

Table 3

The influence (%) of incubation with silage extracts on the survival of KF1 cell line determined with CV assay.

Concentration of silage extract	Type of silage		
	Basic	Hydrated	Commercial
0.25%	94.1 ± 11.1	93.4 ± 8.8	89.2 ± 8.9
0.50%	93.2 ± 8.0	90.2 ± 9.9	85.8 ± 9.8 *
1.00%	85.9 ± 8.7 *	82.4 ± 10.2 *	83.0 ± 9.8 *
2.00%	87.1 ± 9.9 *	85.8 ± 14.9	80.9 ± 5.4 **
4.00%	72.3 ± 6.4 * **	81.7 ± 3.0 ***	79.0 ± 6.5 **

The data were collected 20 h after the end of incubation time. The calculated percentage of cells that survived 2 h incubation with silage extracts is in reference to the survival of cells treated with control medium. Data are presented as mean ± SD, n = 5. The differences between control group and silage extracts-treated groups were significant at: *P ≤ 0.05, ** P ≤ 0.01, *** P ≤ 0.001 (Paired t test).

Table 4

The influence (%) of 2 h incubation with silage extracts on the survival of CCB cell line determined with CV assay.

Concentration of silage extract	Type of silage		
	Basic	Hydrated	Commercial
0.25%	91.9 ± 13.4	95.4 ± 9.4	91.8 ± 12.6
0.50%	84.4 ± 13.3 *	95.7 ± 6.2	89.0 ± 14.1
1.00%	71.9 ± 10.8 ***	87.6 ± 6.2 **	80.4 ± 11.2 **
2.00%	64.0 ± 16.2 **	72.0 ± 6.3 ****	76.5 ± 9.6 ***
4.00%	41.2 ± 17.1 ****	60.3 ± 8.3 ****	59.0 ± 19.5 **

The data were collected 20 h after the end of incubation time. The calculated percentage of cells that survived 2 h incubation with silage extracts is in reference to the survival of cells treated with control medium. Data are presented as mean ± SD, n = 5. The differences between control group and silage extracts-treated groups were significant at: *P ≤ 0.05, ** P ≤ 0.01, *** P ≤ 0.001 (Paired t test).

3.6. Evaluation of CyHV-3 infectivity in fish silages

No activity (no amplification) of CyHV-3 ORFs involved in virus replication was recorded in the CCB and KF1 cell lines (n = 5) treated with DMEM or with the Basic, Hydrated or Commercial silage extracts (Table 5). Both cell lines infected with the virus showed expression of ORFs. Passing the virus through the 0.45 µm syringe filter had no significant effect on the infectivity of CyHV-3.

4. Discussion

Detection of disease agents in farming systems, observed alongside the first clinical signs that precede losses, trigger a set of measures to identify and slow down the spread of the confirmed pathogens, reduce losses and re-adjust biosecurity measures. These actions aim to keep the farm running, prevent the spread of the disease between farms and protect both domestic and wild species in open water systems (EFSA AHAW Panel, 2017). The results of our study are an answer to the questions asked by carp farmers regarding alleviation of costs related to unpredictable and unavoidable mortalities of common carp. Mortalities occur with various frequency and magnitude, are caused by pathogens, predators or other factors, including inadequate nutrition, low water quality, poor management practices, adverse environmental conditions and pollution events (Dixon et al., 2012).

We approached a farm with a confirmed history of KHVD outbreaks in a period of another wave of common carp mass mortalities caused by CyHV-3 to test the feasibility of using fish carcasses to produce

Table 5

The results of RT-qPCR analysis presented as mean Ct values for each analysed CyHV-3 gene and the carp glucokinase gene as control to ensure reaction correctness.

Cell line	Sample	Gene			
		<i>orf78</i>	<i>orf134</i>	<i>orf3</i>	<i>gluc</i>
CCB (n = 5)	Control	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	28.90 ± 1.23
		n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	29.97 ± 1.73
	Basic	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	29.15 ± 1.92
		n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	29.55 ± 0.67
	Hydrated	21.31 ± 0.76	20.06 ± 0.67	26.41 ± 1.62	31.31 ± 1.83
		21.15 ± 0.85	20.29 ± 0.36	27.28 ± 2.09	31.72 ± 2.35
	Commercial	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	29.40 ± 1.26
		n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	29.79 ± 1.19
	Virus	28.64 ± 7.99	27.76 ± 7.73	21.39 ± 3.67	30.32 ± 2.64
		28.53 ± 8.58	25.15 ± 6.68	19.77 ± 2.93	28.82 ± 1.63

Explanations: n.a. – no amplification observed.

pathogen-free organic fertiliser. Cell culture followed by qPCR confirmed that the virus lost its virulence potential to infect CCB and KF1 cells. The virucidal effect of the Basic, Hydrated and Commercial silages on the CyHV-3 activity was possible owing to a combination of physical (low pH) and biological (microorganisms) factors. According to Hartman et al. (2004) and Bondad-Reantaso et al. (2008), disinfection with low-pH solutions (3.0–4.0) is crucial to deactivate a viral agent. Similar conclusions were drawn from susceptibility studies of SVCV (spring viraemia of carp virus) and infectious salmon anaemia virus (ISAV), whose infectivity was shown to be significantly reduced at pH 4 and 3, respectively (Ahne, 1982; Falk et al., 1997). In our study, the lowest pH (4.52) was recorded 21 days after the start of the trial for the Basic silage, and following Dixon et al. (2012), the most resistant viral and bacterial fish pathogens tested (excluding CyHV-3) survive exposure to pH 4.0 for up to 28 days. The authors suggested that acid ensiling used alone was not an effective method of inactivation of many viral and bacterial pathogens. Therefore, the virucidal effect on CyHV-3 in our study was also exerted by the microorganisms present in the three silage types. The microbiome of the silages was not tested, yet as whole fish were minced, it can be assumed that the mixture of bacteria communities from the carp intestine and from the starter culture, along with decreased pH, significantly affected the survival and infectivity of CyHV-3. This assumption is supported by the study by Yoshida et al. (2013) who identified bacterial isolates with anti-KHV activity in the intestinal content of common carp (genera *Aeromonas*, *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Pseudomonas*, *Achromobacter*) and koi carp (genera *Pseudomonas* and *Aeromonas*). Moreover, the study also characterised bacterial isolates with anti-KHV properties (*Pseudomonas* spp.) extracted from water in which fish were kept during the trial. Furthermore, Yoshida et al. (2013) revealed that the virus ceased to be infective after 3 days post addition to intact environmental water while virus added to autoclaved water was infective for at least 7 days. This finding underlines the role of bacteria in virus inactivation. Inactivation of CyHV-3 in the silages could also be possible thanks to exopolysaccharides (EPS) produced by lactic acid bacteria of the genera *Pediococcus*, *Leuconostoc* and *Lactobacillus*, which have been confirmed to exert antiviral activity, also against herpesviruses (Biliavska et al., 2019; Gugliandolo et al., 2015). Reichert

et al. (2017) showed a potential use of EPS from the microalgae strain *Arthrospira platensis* as an additive for aquacultures to decrease or inhibit the spread of KHV and KHVD in future. Other studies identified EPS-producing *Lactobacillus* strains isolated from corn silage, and biochemically characterised two different polymers, i.e., capsular and slime polysaccharides, whose numerous functions include antiviral activity (Tallon et al., 2003).

Another aspect related to the inactivation of CyHV-3 in the silages which supports the arguments raised in the discussion is the absence of live hosts which are crucial to virus persistence and possible infectivity. As suggested by Sunarto et al. (2014), in unfavourable conditions for production of infectious virions, CyHV-3 establishes persistence by inhibiting viral transcription. However, it is expected, but yet to be discovered, that a certain set of viral genes exists which ‘monitors’ host cell regulatory pathways. Specific stimuli (e.g., temperature shift, handling or transportation stress, concurrent infections) to the host activate the CyHV-3 gene expression, recurrent disease and virus transmission (Knipe et al., 2007; Sinclair and Sissons, 2006; Stevens, 1989; Sunarto et al., 2014). In vitro studies by Miest et al. (2015) showed that CyHV-3 does not induce apoptosis in vivo until 14 days post infection. This strategy emphasises the importance of the host in the life cycle of the virus. Our study showed that silaging methods successfully inactivated CyHV-3. Inactivation was concurrently confirmed by the cell cultures (CCB and KF1) and gene expression of KHV genes classified into three temporal kinetic classes (*orf134*, *orf78*, *orf3*). Therefore, final product of the silaging can be considered as safe for further use.

The carp sector in Central Europe currently experiences unavoidable changes exerted by the global aquaculture trends, fish consumer habits, animal welfare campaigns, but also the interest of some carp farmers to update traditional Dubisch-style of farming. Similarly to other marine or freshwater farmers, carp farmers aim to keep their businesses above the profitability threshold, and various solutions are tested to achieve this goal. Raftowicz et al. (2020) analysed the existing supply chains on the Milicz carp market (Barycz Valley, Poland) and showed that future distribution models should be identified in the development of short supply chains. Lasner et al. (2020) proposed that creating a local certified brand can be seen as a successful opportunity to enhance the overall profitability. In our study, we aimed to assess whether silaging might reduce variable costs related to the management of mortalities at fish farms. The silages tested (Basic, Commercial, Hydrated) differed mainly in the components mixed with the fish carcasses to produce the silage. The Hydrated type had the lowest cost (51.45 EUR) per tonne of disposed-of fish compared with Basic (129.79 EUR) and Commercial (463.47 EUR). However, other features like intense and unpleasant odour profile, the highest final pH and additional space needed to implement the Hydrated method on farm scale may be problematic. The production method of the Basic silage type appeared to have optimal parameters to be included in fish farm practice. Moreover, the cost of the Basic method is expected to decrease further if farmers use plants available at fish farms, e.g., hay, vegetation regularly harvested from dykes, pond vegetation (shore and emergent plants) as carbon source, instead of the tested wheat bran. Currently, the cost of disposal of fish mortalities, depending on the agreement between the farm and the waste utilising company, may reach 400 EUR t⁻¹ (direct market inquiry). Instead of incurring costs related to disposal, fish farmers can manage mortalities on-site and produce high-quality fish silage. The proposed in our study the Basic silage type is environmentally friendly and have balanced nutritive properties, thus it may be considered as added value (Olsen and Toppe, 2017).

The mean content of crucial fertiliser’s components (N, P₂O₅ and K) in the Basic silage is higher than in commonly used natural fertilisers, such as slurry and liquid manure of pig and cattle (Maćkowiak, 1997), manure of cattle, pigs, horses and sheep (Maćkowiak and Żebrowski, 2000), and droppings of chickens, geese, ducks and pigeons (Starck, 1997). The level of microelements (e.g., Cu, Mn, Mo,) in the Basic silage was higher than in manure (Koter and Krauze, 1972). The level of heavy

metals (Pb, Cd, Zn) was below the limit set in the Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 laying down rules on making available fertilising products on the European Union (EU) market (European Union, 2019). Therefore, proposed in our study silages (especially Basic type) from dead common carp could be valuable organic fertilisers for agriculture sector.

Recently, the attention to dead fish valorisation has been drawn in EU. The European Parliament and the Council also laid down rules which defined the possible methods to transform dead fish into an organic fertiliser or soil improver via ensiling and composting or into biogas (European Union, 2009). Dead fish, including common carp are considered as Category 2 (high risk) material. Fish farmers interested in reducing total costs of carp farming during daily maintenance check could potentially collect dead fish and use the biomass to produce an organic fertiliser. Proposed in our study solution is an affordable alternative for technologies (e.g. drying) developed for high value species like salmonids. Silaging can improve management of dead fish in freshwater aquaculture sector and reduce the unnecessary costs related to disposal. Further multidirectional studies should focus on assessment the inactivation of other pathogens by the silaging process, e.g. pathogenic strains of bacteria. Moreover, following EU regulations, instead of using chemical stimulants, different application forms (e.g. pellets) of the natural biostimulants made of silage should be further explored (Madende and Hayes, 2020).

5. Conclusions

To our knowledge, there are no published data on the survival of CyHV-3 following silaging. The study showed that without costly and operationally difficult solutions dead carp can be transformed into highly valuable fertiliser. The method is straightforward and highly flexible, as unexpected mortality events of various size and frequency can be easily managed, while the organic fertiliser produced is safe in terms of pathogens. Although we tested the survival and infectivity potential of CyHV-3, in our opinion mortalities induced by other pathogens might also be successfully converted into a valuable and safe organic fertiliser or soil improver. The initial results of the study have been discussed with carp farmers who supported the proposed silaging method to decrease the unexpected costs related to utilisation of dead fish and acknowledged the significance of the idea in terms of sustainable freshwater aquaculture and strengthening the cooperation within the aqua-agri network.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Remigiusz Panicz: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration and Funding acquisition. **Piotr Eljasik:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Software, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Agnieszka Troszok:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Małgorzata Sobczak:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Stawomir Lisiecki:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Arkadiusz Nędzarek:** Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Jacek Sadowski:** Investigation, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 funding programme under Grant Agreement no. 773330 (GAIN). We assume that country should be stated as European Union, since it was project carried out by international consortium and funding was given by European Commission.

The authors wish to thank all lab and fish farm members who assisted in experiments. The authors would like to thank Dr Mikotaj Adamek and Prof. Dieter Steinhagen (Fish Disease Research Unit, University of Veterinary Medicine, Hannover) for generously providing the KF1 cell line.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.aqrep.2022.101116](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2022.101116).

References

- Ababneh, M., Hananeh, W., Alzghoul, M., 2020. Mass mortality associated with koi herpesvirus in common carp in Iraq. *Heliyon* 6 (8), e04827. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04827>.
- Adamek, M., Rauch, G., Brogden, G., Steinhagen, D., 2014. Small interfering RNA treatment can inhibit Cyprinid herpesvirus 3 associated cell death in vitro. *Pol. J. Vet. Sci.* 17 (4), 733–735. <https://doi.org/10.2478/pjvs-2014-0108>.
- Ahmadvand, S., Soltani, M., Shokrpour, S., Rahmati-Holasoo, H., El-Matbouli, M., Taheri-Mirghaed, A., 2020. Cyprinid herpesvirus 3 (CyHV-3) transmission and outbreaks in Iran: detection and characterization in farmed common carp. *Microb. Pathog.* 149, 104321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2020.104321>.
- Ahne, W., 1982. Comparative studies on the stability of four fish-pathogenic viruses (VHSV, PFR, SVCV, IPNV). *Zent. für Vet.* 29, 457–476.
- Bercovier, H., Fishman, Y., Nahary, R., Sinai, S., Zlotkin, A., Eyngor, M., Gilad, O., Eldar, A., Hedrick, R.P., 2005. Cloning of the koi herpesvirus (KHV) gene encoding thymidine kinase and its use for a highly sensitive PCR based diagnosis. *BMC Microbiol.* 5 (1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2180-5-13>.
- Bergmann, S.M., Jin, Y., Franzke, K., Grunow, B., Wang, Q., Klafack, S., 2020. Koi herpesvirus (KHV) and KHV disease (KHVD)-a recently updated overview. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 129 (1), 98–103. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14616>.
- Bergmann, S.M., Kemptner, J., Sadowski, J., Fichtner, D., 2006. First detection, confirmation and isolation of koi herpesvirus (KHV) in cultured common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.) in Poland. *Bull.-Eur. Assoc. Fish. Pathol.* 26 (2), 97.
- Biliavska, L., Pankivska, Y., Povnitsa, O., Zagorodnya, S., 2019. Antiviral activity of exopolysaccharides produced by lactic acid bacteria of the genera *Pediococcus*, *Leuconostoc* and *Lactobacillus* against Human Adenovirus Type 5. *Medicina* 55 (9), 519. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina55090519>.
- Bondad-Reantaso, M.G., Mohan, C.V., Crumlish, M. & Subasinghe, R.P. (2008). *Diseases in Asian Aquaculture VI*. Manila, Fish Health Section, Asian Fisheries Society.
- Boutier, M., Gao, Y., Vancsok, C., Suárez, N.M., Davison, A.J., Vanderplassen, A., 2017. Identification of an essential virulence gene of Cyprinid herpesvirus 3. *Antivir. Res.* 145, 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.antiviral.2017.07.002>.
- Boutier, M., Ronsmans, M., Ouyang, P., Fournier, G., Reschner, A., Rakus, K., Wilkie, G. S., Farnir, F., Bayrou, C., Lieffrig, F., Li, H., Desmecht, D., Davison, A.J., Vanderplassen, A., 2015. Rational development of an attenuated recombinant cyprinid herpesvirus 3 vaccine using prokaryotic mutagenesis and in vivo bioluminescent imaging. *Plos Pathog* 11 (2), e1004690. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1004861>.
- Bush, S.R., Van Zwieten, P.A., Visser, L., van Dijk, H., Bosma, R., de Boer, W.F., Verdegem, M., 2010. Scenarios for resilient shrimp aquaculture in tropical coastal areas. *Ecol. Soc.* 15 (2), 15. (<http://www.jstor.org/stable/26268149>).
- Desai, A.S., Brennan, M., Gangan, S.S., Brennan, C., 2022. Utilization of Fish Waste as a Value-Added Ingredient: Sources and Bioactive Properties of Fish Protein Hydrolysate. *Sustainable Fish Production and Processing*. Academic Press, pp. 203–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-824296-4.00004-9>.
- Dishon, A., Perelberg, A., Bishara-Shieban, J., Ilouze, M., Davidovich, M., Werker, S., Kotler, M., 2005. Detection of carp interstitial nephritis and gill necrosis virus in fish droppings. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 71 (11), 7285–7291. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.11.7285-7291.2005>.
- Dixon, P.F., Joiner, C.L., Way, K., Reese, R.A., Jeney, G., Jeney, Z., 2009. Comparison of the resistance of selected families of common carp, *Cyprinus carpio* L., to koi herpesvirus: preliminary study. *J. Fish. Dis.* 32 (12), 1035–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2761.2009.01081.x>.
- Dixon, P.F., Small, D.A., Algoët, M., Hastings, T.S., Bayley, A., Byrne, H., Byrne, H., Dodge, M., Garden, A., Joiner, C., Roberts, E., Verner-Jeffreys, D., Thompson, F., 2012. Studies on the effect of temperature and pH on the inactivation of fish viral and bacterial pathogens. *J. Fish. Dis.* 35 (1), 51–64. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2761.2011.01324.x>.
- EFSA AHAW Panel (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare), More, S., Bøtner, A., Butterworth, A., Calistri, P., Depner, K., Edwards, S., Garin-Bastuji, B., Good, M., Gortazar Schmidt, C., Michel, V., Miranda, M. A., Nielsen, S. S., Raj, M., Sihvonen, L., Spooler, H., Stegeman, J. A., Thulke, H., -H., Velarde, A., Willeberg, P., Winckler, C., Baldinelli, F., Broglia, A., Zancanaro, G., Beltran Beck, B., Kohnle, L., Morgado, J., & Bicout, D. (2017). Scientific Opinion on the assessment of listing and categorisation of animal diseases within the framework of the Animal Health Law (Regulation (EU) No 2016/429): Koi herpes virus disease (KHV). *EFSA Journal*, 15 (7), 4907. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4907>.
- Eide, K.E., Miller-Morgan, T., Heidel, J.R., Kent, M.L., Bildfell, R.J., Lapatra, S., Watson, G., Jin, L., 2011. Investigation of koi herpesvirus latency in koi. *J. Virol.* 85 (10), 4954–4962. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01384-10>.
- European Union, 2009. Commission Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 of 21 October 2009 laying down health rules as regards animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1774/2002 (Animal by-products Regulation). *Off. J. Eur. Union* 52, 1–34.
- European Union, 2019. Regulation No 1009 of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003. *Off. J. Eur. Union* 62, 1–15.
- Fabian, M., Baumer, A., Steinhagen, D., 2013. Do wild fish species contribute to the transmission of koi herpesvirus to carp in hatchery ponds? *J. Fish. Dis.* 36 (5), 505–514. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfd.12016>.
- Falk, K., Namork, E., Rimstad, E., Mjåland, S., Dannevig, B.H., 1997. Characterization of infectious salmon anemia virus, an orthomyxo-like virus isolated from Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.). *J. Virol.* 71 (12), 9016–9023. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.71.12.9016-9023.1997>.
- FAO, 2020. The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020. Sustainability in action. Rome. (<http://www.fao.org/3/cb5186en/cb5186en.pdf>), (accessed on 06.09.2021).
- FAO FishStat, 2022. Fisheries and Aquaculture Software. FishStatPlus – Universal Software for Fishery Statistical Time Series. FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Department (online), Rome. Retrieved from (www.fao.org/fishery/2022-03-08).
- Fournier, G., Boutier, M., Raj, V.S., Mast, J., Parmentier, E., Vanderwalle, P., Peeters, D., Lieffrig, F., Farnir, F., Gillet, L., Vanderplassen, A., 2012. Feeding *Cyprinus carpio* with infectious materials mediates cyprinid herpesvirus 3 entry through infection of pharyngeal periodontal mucosa. *Vet. Res.* 43 (1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9716-43-6>.
- Gao, Y., Lo, K.V., Liao, P.H., 1992. Utilization of salmon farm mortalities: fish silage. *Bioresour. Technol.* 41 (2), 123–127. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-8524\(92\)90181-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-8524(92)90181-V).
- Gilad, O., Yun, S., Adkison, M.A., Way, K., Willits, N.H., Bercovier, H., Hedrick, R.P., 2003. Molecular comparison of isolates of an emerging fish pathogen, koi herpesvirus, and the effect of water temperature on mortality of experimentally infected koi. *J. Gen. Virol.* 84 (19), 2661–2667. <https://doi.org/10.1099/vir.0.19323-0>.
- Gilad, O., Yun, S., Zagmutt-Vergara, F., Leutenegger, C., Bercovier, H., Hedrick, R., 2004. Concentrations of a Koi herpesvirus (KHV) in tissues of experimentally-infected *Cyprinus carpio* koi as assessed by real-time TaqMan PCR. *Dis. Aquat. Org.* 60, 179–187. <https://doi.org/10.3354/dao060179>.
- Gugliandolo, C., Spanò, A., Maueri, T.L., Poli, A., Arena, A., Nicolaus, B., 2015. Role of bacterial exopolysaccharides as agents in counteracting immune disorders induced by herpes virus. *Microorganisms* 3, 464–483. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms3030464>.
- Hanson, L., Dishon, A., Kotler, M., 2011. Herpesviruses that infect fish. *Viruses* 3 (11), 2160–2191. <https://doi.org/10.3390/v3112160>.
- Hartman, K.H., Yanong, R.P., Petty, B.D., Francis-Floyd, R., Riggs, A.C., 2004. Koi herpes virus (KHV) disease. Fact sheet VM-149, Extension service, Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences. University of Florida, <https://edis.ifas.ufl.edu/pdffiles/VM/VM11300.pdf>.
- Hedrick, R.P., Gilad, O., Yun, S., Spangenberg, J.V., Marty, G.D., Nordhausen, R.W., Kebus, M., Bercovier, H., Eldar, A., 2000. A herpesvirus associated with mass mortality of juvenile and adult koi, a strain of common carp. *J. Aquat. Anim. Health* 12 (1), 44–57. [https://doi.org/10.1577/1548-8667\(2000\)012<0044:AHAWMM>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1577/1548-8667(2000)012<0044:AHAWMM>2.0.CO;2).
- Jansen, P.A., Kristoffersen, A.B., Viljugrein, H., Jimenez, D., Aldrin, M., Stien, A., 2012. Sea lice as a density-dependent constraint to salmonid farming. *Proc. R. Soc. B: Biol. Sci.* 279, 2330–2338. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.0084>.
- Jastrzębska, A., 2009. Modifications of spectrophotometric methods for total phosphorus determination in meat samples. *Chem. Pap.* 63 (1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.2478/s11696-008-0091-2>.
- Johansen, L.H., Jensen, I., Mikkelsen, H., Bjørn, P.A., Jansen, P.A., Bergh, Ø., 2011. Disease interaction and pathogens exchange between wild and farmed fish populations with special reference to Norway. *Aquaculture* 315 (3–4), 167–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2011.02.014>.
- Kelly, D.W., Paterson, R.A., Townsend, C.R., Poulin, R., Tompkins, D.M., 2009. Parasite spillback: a neglected concept in invasion ecology? *Ecology* 90 (8), 2047–2056. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1085.1>.
- Kibenge, S.B., Godoy, M.G., 2016. *Aquaculture Virology*. Academic Press,, Amsterdam.
- Knipe, D.M., Howley, P.M., Griffin, D.E., Lamb, R.A., Martin, M.A., Roizman, B., Straus, S.E., 2007. *Fields Virology*, fifth ed. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins,, Philadelphia.
- Koter, M., Krauze, A., 1972. Skład chemiczny obornika pochodzącego z woj. olsztyńskiego. *Rocz. Glebozn.* 23 (2), 291–297.

- Krkošek, M., Lewis, M.A., Morton, A., Frazer, L.N., Volpe, J.P., 2006. Epizootics of wild fish induced by farm fish. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 103, 15506–15510. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0603525103>.
- Lasner, T., Mytlewski, A., Nourry, M., Rakowski, M., Oberle, M., 2020. Carp land: economics of fish farms and the impact of region-marketing in the Aischgrund (DEU) and Barycz Valley (POL). *Aquaculture* 519, 734731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.734731>.
- Latimer, G.W., 2019. Official method of analysis of AOAC™ by AOAC international 21st Edition, MD, USA.
- Leung, T.L., Bates, A.E., 2013. More rapid and severe disease outbreaks for aquaculture at the tropics: implications for food security. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 215–222. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2644.12017>.
- Mačkowiak, C., 1997. Rola nawożenia organicznego w kształtowaniu żyzności i urodzajności gleby, Materiały szkoleniowe 63/97., Puławy, Instytut Uprawy, Nawożenia i Gleboznawstwa.
- Mačkowiak, C., Zebrowski, J., 2000. Skład chemiczny obornika w Polsce. *Nawoz. i Nawoz.* 4 (5), 119–130.
- Madende, M., Hayes, M., 2020. Fish by-product use as biostimulants: an overview of the current state of the art, including relevant legislation and regulations within the EU and USA. *Molecules* 25, 1122. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25051122>.
- Miest, J.J., Adamek, M., Pionnier, N., Harris, S., Matras, M., Rakus, K.L., Irnazarow, I., Steinhagen, D., Hoole, D., 2015. Differential effects of alloherpesvirus CyHV-3 and rhabdovirus SVCV on apoptosis in fish cells. *Vet. Microbiol.* 176 (1–2), 19–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2014.12.012>.
- Minamoto, T., Honjo, M.N., Kawabata, Z., 2009. Seasonal distribution of cyprinid herpesvirus 3 in Lake Biwa, Japan. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 75 (21), 6900–6904. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01411-09>.
- Ministry of Economy, 2010. Rozporządzenie Ministra Gospodarki z dnia 8 września 2010 r. w sprawie sposobu pakowania nawozów mineralnych, umieszczania informacji o składnikach nawozowych na tych opakowaniach, sposobu badania nawozów mineralnych oraz typów wapna nawozowego, Dz.U. 2010, nr 183, poz. 1229. Retrieved from (<http://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20101831229>) 2020–10-31.
- Mistri, M., Munari, C., Pagnoni, A., Chenet, T., Pasti, L., Cavazzini, A., 2020. Accumulation of trace metals in crayfish tissues: is *Procambarus clarkii* a vector of pollutants in Po Delta inland waters? *Eur. Zool. J.* 87 (1), 46–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24750263.2020.1717653>.
- Olsen, R.L., Toppe, J., 2017. Fish silage hydrolysates: Not only a feed nutrient, but also a useful feed additive. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 66, 93–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2017.06.003>.
- Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S., & Szczubińska, Z. (1991). Metody analizy i oceny właściwości gleb i roślin. Katalog. Instytut Ochrony Środowiska, Warszawa, Polska.
- Panicz, R., Eljasik, P., Śmietana, N., Sadowski, J., Biernaczyk, M., 2020. New invertebrate species as potential CyHV-3 reservoirs: a case study of common carp mortalities in hyperthermal conditions. *J. Fish. Dis.* 43 (7), 821–824. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfd.13177>.
- Perelberg, A., Ilouze, M., Kotler, M., Steinitz, M., 2008. Antibody response and resistance of *Cyprinus carpio* immunized with *Cyprinid herpesvirus-3* (CyHV-3). *Vaccine* 26 (29), 3750–3756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2008.04.057>.
- PN-ISO 6658:1998. Analiza sensoryczna. Metodologia. Wytyczne ogólne.
- Raftowicz, M., Kalisiak-Mędelska, M., Struś, M., 2020. Redefining the supply chain model on the millicz carp market. *Sustainability* 12 (7), 2934. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12072934>.
- Rahmati-Holasoo, H., Zargar, A., Ahmadiand, S., Shokrpoo, S., Ezhari, S., Ebrahimzadeh Mousavi, H.A., 2016. First detection of koi herpesvirus from koi, *Cyprinus carpio* L. experiencing mass mortalities in Iran: clinical, histopathological and molecular study. *J. Fish. Dis.* 39 (10), 1153–1163. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfd.12448>.
- Rakus, K.L., Irnazarow, I., Adamek, M., Palmeira, L., Kawana, Y., Hirono, I., Kondo, H., Matras, M., Steinhagen, D., Flasz, B., Brogden, G., Vanderplasschen, A., Aoki, T., 2012. Gene expression analysis of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.) lines during Cyprinid herpesvirus 3 infection yields insights into differential immune responses. *Dev. Comp. Immunol.* 37 (1), 65–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dci.2011.12.006>.
- Ramakrishnan, M.A., 2016. Determination of 50% endpoint titer using a simple formula. *World J. Virol.* 5 (2), 85–86. <https://doi.org/10.5501/wjv.v5.i2.85>.
- Reichert, M., Bergmann, S.M., Hwang, J., Buchholz, R., Lindenberger, C., 2017. Antiviral activity of exopolysaccharides from *Arthrospira platensis* against koi herpesvirus. *J. Fish. Dis.* 40 (10), 1441–1450. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfd.12618>.
- Salama, N.K.G., Murray, A.G., 2011. Farm size as a factor in hydrodynamic transmission of pathogens in aquaculture fish production. *Aquac. Environ. Interact.* 2, 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.3354/aei00030>.
- Saotome, K., Morita, H., Umeda, M., 1989. Cytotoxicity test with simplified crystal violet staining method using microtitre plates and its application to injection drugs. *Toxicol. Vitro* 3 (4), 317–321. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0887-2333\(89\)90039-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0887-2333(89)90039-8).
- Shimizu, T., Yoshida, N., Kasai, H., Yoshimizu, M., 2006. Survival of Koi Herpesvirus (KHV) in environmental water. *Fish. Pathol.* 41 (4), 153–157. <https://doi.org/10.3147/jfsp.41.153>.
- Shinn, A.J., Pratoomyot, J., Bron, J., Paladini, G., Brooker, E., Brooker, A., 2015. Economic impacts of aquatic parasites on global finfish production. *Glob. Aquac. Advocate* 2015, 58–61. (<http://pdf.gaalliance.org/pdf/GAA-Shinn-Sept15.pdf>).
- Sinclair, J., Sissons, P., 2006. Latency and reactivation of human cytomegalovirus. *J. Gen. Virol.* 87 (7), 1763–1779. <https://doi.org/10.1099/vir.0.81891-0>.
- Sosa-Villalobos, C., del Refugio Castañeda-Chávez, M., Amaro-Espejo, I.A., Galaviz-Villa, I., Lango-Reynoso, F., 2016. Diagnosis of the current state of aquaculture production systems with regard to the environment in Mexico. *Lat. Am. J. Aquat. Res.* 44 (2), 193–201. <https://doi.org/10.3856/vol44-issue2-fulltext-1>.
- Starck J.R., 1997. *Uprawa roli i nawożenie roślin ogrodniczych*. Warszawa, Państwowe Wydawnictwo Rolnicze i Leśne.
- Stevens, J.G., 1989. Human herpesviruses: a consideration of the latent state. *Microbiol. Rev.* 53 (3), 318–332.
- Sunarto, A., McColl, K.A., Crane, M.S.J., Schat, K.A., Slobedman, B., Barnes, A.C., Walker, P.J., 2014. Characteristics of cyprinid herpesvirus 3 in different phases of infection: implications for disease transmission and control. *Virus Res.* 188, 45–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virusres.2014.03.024>.
- Tadmor-Levi, R., Asoulin, E., Hulata, G., David, L., 2017. Studying the genetics of resistance to CyHV-3 disease using introgression from feral to cultured common carp strains. *Front. Genet.* 8 (24), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2017.00024>.
- Tallon, R., Bressollier, P., Urdaci, M.C., 2003. Isolation and characterization of two exopolysaccharides produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum* EP56. *Res. Microbiol.* 154 (10), 705–712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2003.09.006>.
- Troszok, A., Kolek, L., Szczygiel, J., Wawrzeczko, J., Borzym, E., Reichert, M., Kamińska, T., Ostrowski, T., Jurecka, P., Adamek, M., Rakus, K.L., Irnazarow, I., 2018. Acyclovir inhibits Cyprinid herpesvirus 3 multiplication in vitro. *J. Fish. Dis.* 41 (11), 1709–1718. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfd.12880>.
- Walster, C., 1999. Clinical observations of severe mortalities in koi carp, *Cyprinus carpio*, with gill disease. *Fish. Vet. J.* 3, 54–58.
- Wickham, H., 2016. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. Springer-Verlag, New York.
- Yoshida, N., Sasaki, R.K., Kasai, H., Yoshimizu, M., 2013. Inactivation of koi-herpesvirus in water using bacteria isolated from carp intestines and carp habitats. *J. Fish. Dis.* 36 (12), 997–1005. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2761.2012.01449.x>.